

THE DEVELOPMENT OF LAB-GROWN MEAT WHICH WILL LEAD TO THE NEXT FARMING REVOLUTION

Dr. A. SHAJI GEORGE

Independent Researcher, Masters IT Solutions, Chennai -600 057, Tamil Nadu, India

E-mail: [1drashajigeorge@gmail.com](mailto:¹drashajigeorge@gmail.com)

ABSTRACT

Cultured or Lab-grown meat has its place in the developing field of cellular agriculture and constitutes a hopeful technology to provide products that have so far created through livestock. This innovative technology seeks to offer a chance of decreasing the negative impacts of present meat production as well as consumption on humans, the environment, and livestock. Lab-grown meat provides a safe and infection-free path forward to meet the growing meat necessity without the involvement of animal killing while at the same time decreasing greenhouse emissions, as compared to traditional meat. The whole research has been based on secondary sources. Data has been compiled from several publications about livestock as well as lab-grown meat. The objective of the following research article has been to assess the effect of the lab-grown meat Industry on traditional meat across the sector. The following article focuses on how it will help our growing population, the use of new lab-grown meat is cheaper and affordable to the people compared to traditional meat, the positive impact on human health, how it will help to decrease the carbon emissions, save water, prevents animal cruelty, agricultural Industrialization, and labour market. Lab-grown meat It will not only enhance the production of meat products but then additionally enhance their value. This paper summarizes several important positive characteristics of the lab-grown meat and the history that has led to the New meat revolution. The research explores its impact on the global and Indian farming production system and the consumer market.

Keywords: *Lab-Grown Meat, Cultured Meat, Slaughter free, Cellular Agriculture, Farming Sector, Government policy, Meat Consumption and Religion, Greenhouse Emissions.*

INTRODUCTION

Meat intake around the world in both developed and developing countries has been on the rise. During the second half of the 20th century, worldwide meat consumption grew by five times as much, increasing from Forty-five million tonnes of meat eaten in 1950 to nearly Three hundred million tonnes now. As a consequence of estimated population increase and growth in welfare, meat demand is expected to grow by 75% around 2050, whilst production of meat through livestock could stay sluggish, more food will be required to satisfy the demand of the increasing population, which is a big challenge because of the resources and agricultural land limitations.

India has the world's largest livestock population across the country. It possesses 512.0 million of the animal population except for poultry. India is the world's largest exporter of buffalo meat as well as the third-largest exporter of meat. It accounts for approximately 58 percent of the world's buffalo population as well as 14.7 percent of cattle population. There are around 300 million bovine animals, 135.2 million goats, 65.07million sheep, and approximately 10.3million pigs as well as 729.2 million poultry in the nation in accordance with the 19th Livestock Census. Animal production of beef is especially unproductive, as livestock achieves a conversion rate of feed to the animal protein content of roughly 15 percent. Pigs might reach a conversion rate of 30 percent and chickens reach much higher rates. Livestock consumes a substantial portion of our natural food resources that we can use to directly feed people, and which could possibly reduce food scarcity at a global level.

Additionally, livestock provides significantly to greenhouse gas (GHG) emission, specifically methane emitted by ruminants. It is calculated that livestock agriculture provides up to 15percent of overall GHG emissions. The figures are disturbing, although they also offer an opportunity to enhance the existing production system as well as revert several of the negative consequences of meat production. Moreover, we might be able to seek a global decrease in meat demand by encouraging vegetarianism or a strict limit in meat consumption, although success is not likely provided the constant tiny size of the vegetarian population in industrial meat-consuming nations. Additionally, meat equivalents from vegetable protein sources, so far, do not manage to capture a significant market share outside the traditional vegetarian target population.

The development of lab-grown beef from bovine skeletal muscle stem cells via tissue-engineering techniques is possibly a resource-effective way to grow meat. For lab-grown beef and poultry to turn into a sustainable alternative to livestock meat, its production will need to be resource-efficient, scalable, sustainable, and will lead to a product that is impossible to differentiate from natural meat. Additionally, customers will have to accept lab-grown meat as a valuable and eventually desirable equal to the natural product. Consequently, more effective methods of protein production are currently being developed to maintain the increasing global population at the same time and are in compliance with the current challenges, for example, the environmental and animal welfare issues. Amongst the solution to the problem, lab-grown meat is being presented by its supporters as a viable alternative for consumers who wish to be more accountable but do not want to alter the composition of their diet. Such challenges are difficult but likely manageable. The seriousness of the future food security dangers justifies the serious research and development efforts to tackle the challenges that come along with producing lab-grown meat to the market.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

The primary objective of the paper is to speak about the expected changes in the farming sector because of Lab-grown meat, this research seeks to explore the information transmitted in initial media and publication coverage of lab-grown meat. The current research is based upon the following objectives.

- To analyze how lab-grown meat will feed our growing population.
- To Visualize the cost of lab-grown meat, the impact on the global consumer market, and the Indian economy.
- To find out the developments of Lab-grown meat revolution.
- Detailed analysis of the advantages of lab-grown meat to the world.
- To study the societal and ethical effects of lab-grown meat revolution.
- The Evaluation of the environmental impacts of lab-grown meat.
- Suggestions concerning proactive measures for lab-grown meat.

METHODOLOGY:

This research primarily uses secondary data. Information that is used for the research was solely based on secondary sources from different publications. The appropriate sources of information gathered are published and unpublished sources such as books, magazines, journals, reports, publications, and the website of numerous online journals, etc. Most editorials examined for this study have been compiled utilizing Online Newspapers, Articles, and Blog database. The main terms used to look up appropriate articles contained “meat” in the headline as well as “Lab-grown meat” in every text.

ABOUT LAB -GROWN MEAT

Presently, there are many emerging companies rushing into this ever-expanding market of lab-grown meats, ready to produce food that competes with even a few of your favorite food. Supported by key players such as Bill Gates and even Cargill agricultural company, these firms produce a host of meats including, beef, poultry, pork, and seafood. Clean meat, also called lab-grown meat, in vitro, or cultured meat is meat that is cultivated in cell culture, instead of from an animal’s body. Potential advantages of lab-grown meat consist of sustainability, animal welfare, environmental friendliness, novel foods, as well as food safety.

ABOUT PLANT-BASED MEAT

Plant-based meat is not identical to lab-based meat. On the Other Hand, it replicates the flavor and texture of actual sausage, beef, as well as other meats without having to use any animal products. They accomplish this by using unique recipes and food preparation. For example, companies ferment genetically engineered yeast to produce heme a protein that is crucial to duplicating the flavor, juiciness, and color of real meat.

HISTORY OF LAB GROWN MEAT (CULTURED MEAT)

Across years of research, trials, as well as countless hours of work carried out by several scientists, (Cultured) lab-grown meats were created.

What follows is a timeline of when and how the genetically made meat has come about:

YEAR	EVENT
1998	Jon Vein acquires a patent for the manufacturing of lab-grown meat tissue meant for the purpose of human intake.
2001	NASA starts trials creating cultured meats by starter cells derived from turkeys.
2001	Businessman Willem van Kooten, Medical doctor Willem van Eelen and dermatologist Wieta Westerhof, mutually file a patent relating to their method of creating cultured meat for human consumption.
2002	The first edible lab-grown meat (Cultured) sample is produced: a fish fillet produced from cultured goldfish cells.
2003	Harvard Medical School and Tissue Culture and Art Project used stem cells derived from frogs to produce tissue which resembled a steak.
2008	PETA provides one million dollars to the initial company that could bring lab-grown chicken for the food industry.
2009	Time magazine labels cultured meat (Lab-Grown) as one of the breakthrough concepts of the year.
2013	The world's first lab-grown (Cultured) beef hamburger was consumed during a press event. The hamburger has been created by Dr. Mark Post at Maastricht University in the Netherlands, and the event has been hosted in London, England.
2015	Maastricht University conducted its first International Conference on (Lab-Grown) Cultured Meat.
2016	An engineered meat startup company, Memphis Meats, posts a promo video presenting their lab-grown meatballs.
2016	An Israeli company, SuperMeat, operates a crowdfunding campaign to raise funds for their attempts to bring lab-grown poultry products to the market.
2017	Finless Foods has announced that they anticipate bringing sustainable, lab-grown seafood to customer markets within two years.
2018	Dutch startup company Meatable claims they would be able to produce cultured meat derived from stem cells taken from the animal umbilical cords, resolving the problem of needing to kill an animal originally to get starter cells for production.

LAB- GROWN MEAT PROCESS

Lab-grown meat is created by using small tissue from an animal. The Tissue is filtered and isolated for cells that can be grown. It will subsequently be provided warmth and oxygen, fed salt, sugar, and protein in cell culture. Essentially, the scientists deceive the cell into thinking that it's still in the animal. Then it will naturally duplicate, grow muscle, fat, and connective tissue, and then turn into our food.

LAB GROWN MEAT – PROCESS (COW)

LAB GROWN MEAT – PROCESS (PIG)

LAB GROWN MEAT – PROCESS (CHICKEN)

LAB GROWN MEAT WILL HELP FEED OUR GROWING POPULATION

Meat demand is growing rapidly. In 2050, the global population will exceed more than nine billion, and the meat demand is projected to be 70 percent more than the present level, according to figures from the United Nations of Food and Agriculture Organization. We have already utilized the vast majority of farmland for livestock rearing. Moreover, water scarcity is an increasing problem towards which livestock contributes substantially. It is straightforward to estimate that we simply do not have sufficient land and water to boost meat production by 70 percentage using livestock. This implies that we either need to cut down on our consumption of meat, or else find a more effective way to produce it. It is anticipated that cultured meat (Lab grown meat) production is going to use up to 99 percent less land, and 96 percent less water. This larger effectiveness will provide an opportunity to supply the world's increasing population with genuine meat in a sustainable manner.

LAB GROWN MEAT WILL BE CHEAPER IN THE NEAR FUTURE

The industrial livestock industry has been one of the world's oldest, biggest, as well as the most ineffective food manufacturing systems throughout the world. Modern ingredients as well as food products are roughly ten times more effective throughout the board from the land and water use to feedstock intake and energy consumption. Precision fermentation (PF) is a process that allows the programming of micro-organisms to form almost any complex organic molecule. Its costs are falling down at an exponential rate due to rapid advancements in underlying biological as well as information technologies. The expense to create a single molecule using PF has dropped from \$1 million per kilogram in 2000 to approximately \$100 today. On The Assumption that the current technologies and use properly established cost curves, the report projects that these costs will drop below \$10 per kilogram by 2025, these proteins shall be five times cheaper than conventional animal proteins by 2030 as well as 10 times cheaper in 2035. In 2030, modern-day food products are going to cost less than half as much to manufacture as the animal-derived products which they replace. At the same moment, such a new production system has the ability to encourage competition. and fast iteration of products which are always cheaper as well as ever improved more nutritious, better tasting, healthier, more diverse, and more convenient, if open markets as well as the nutritional standards are protected.

THE ADVANTAGE OF LAB-GROWN MEAT'S QUICK PRODUCTION

The present traditional meat production methods are ineffective in terms of nutrition as well as energy use which will also take a long time for conversion with months for chickens as well as years for pigs and cows before the meat can be harvested and available in the market. Lab-grown meat uses a significantly shorter time compare to the traditional meat, which takes many weeks rather than months for chickens or even years for pigs and cows before the meat could be harvested.

ADVANTAGES OF LAB GROWN MEAT (CULTURED MEAT)

<p>MAJOR JOB OPPORTUNITY</p>		
<p>HEALTHIER FOOD</p>		
<p>GLOBAL HUNGER COULD BE REDUCED</p>		
<p>SAVE FROM BACTERIAL CONTAMINATION</p>		
<p>LOW SATURATED FAT</p>		

LAB GROWN MEAT - POSITIVE IMPACTS ON HUMAN HEALTH

The transition from traditional meat to lab-grown meat (Clean Meat) might have a beneficial effect on human health. Livestock products are the human diet’s main source of saturated fat, which is associated with health problems like heart disease and strokes. Lab-grown meat can be a superb practical food due to the fact that it can be modified to change the profile of vital amino acids and fats, which will be supplemented in vitamins, minerals as well as bioactive compounds so as to ensure that it not only is in balanced amounts of natural meat but then also surpasses it to cover up particular nutritional requirements for individuals with various illnesses. The nutritional value of lab-grown meat might be regulated to improve the nutritious content, which leads to an improvement in consumer health. Animals are frequently fed antibiotics to help prevent disease this issue has been associated with the emergence of antibiotic-resistance within the bacteria strains which infect humans, leading India to present regulations to limit antibiotic usage in farming. Lab-grown meat would not need the use of antibiotics, which might have a positive impact on future

public health. Circumstances in factory farms, as well as slaughterhouses, are usually unhygienic, and then contact with infected meat may lead to the proliferation of harmful disease-causing bacteria like Escherichia coli and salmonella. Growing meat in laboratory conditions can restrict the number of humans contaminated.

LAB-GROWN MEAT WILL STOP ANIMAL CRUELTY

Around 70 billion animals are farmed yearly throughout the world, nearly 50 billion of them are farmed in farming plants. Such animals are being treated in the same way as gears in a machine than living animals. They suffer a short, miserable life and are frequently squeezed together in cages, pens, or crates in which they are not able to participate in their natural behavior. Several animals are bred in a selective manner to be rapidly growing, weakened, disabled, and fractured bones, infections, and multiple organ failure remain common. Lab-grown meat will not require the slaughter of animals. On the Other Hand, lab-grown meat is produced by growing cells that are extracted from a live animal using a tiny biopsy done using anesthesia, which does not cause any damage to the animal. Lab-grown meat has the possibility to put an end to the suffering of billions of livestock each year.

Number of animals slaughtered for meat, World, 2018

Source: UN Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO)
 Note: This is based on livestock production for meat (and therefore does not include dairy or egg production).

CC BY

LAB GROWN MEAT IS BENEFICIAL FOR OUR ENVIRONMENT

Livestock farming generates 15 percent of greenhouse gas emissions, according to data from the Food and Agriculture Organisation of the UN. This is comparable to the whole transport sector which includes all cars as well as planes. Moreover, cattle and their manure produce methane, which is 30-40 times more powerful than carbon-dioxide like a heat-trapping gas. Lab-grown meat produces up to 96 percent less greenhouse gas emissions, assisting us to prevent the catastrophic effects of climate change. Beyond climate change, animal production has a certain number of other severe impacts on the environment. We are using large quantities of pasturable as well as arable land to raise and nourish livestock, leading in several extraordinary instances to mass deforestation. Large portions of the Amazon rainforest have now been cleared for livestock, for example. This will in turn lead to a severe loss of biological diversity. Every day we're losing upwards of 80,000 acres of tropical rainforest, and along with it approximately 135 plant, livestock, and insect species.

Land use per kilogram of food product

Land use is measured in meters squared (m²) per kilogram of a given food product.

Source: Poore, J., & Nemecek, T. (2018). Reducing food's environmental impacts through producers and consumers. CC BY
 Note: Data represents the global average land use of food products based on a large meta-analysis of food production covering 38,700 commercially viable farms in 119 countries.

That is 50,000 species getting wiped out each year. An additional issue is agricultural pollution, triggered by the release into the environment of drainages like pesticides and fertilizers, resulting in overloaded waterways, and then running into the rivers and oceans. Once there, a runoff will be able to kill aquatic life as well as coral reefs and still cause dead zones, low oxygen areas in which aquatic life suffocates and then dies. Lab-grown meat production is the greater environmentally

friendly kind of production, that does not require the use of chemical substances and is carried out in a closed system, avoiding runoff from entering into the natural environment.

*Usage, Emissions, Cost per pound of meat
Sources : CB Insights, Water footprint Network, Business Insider, Forbes, Food Climate Research Network (FCRN), Quartz*

LAB GROWN MEAT REQUIRES LESS WATER AND PREVENTS WATER POLLUTION

Lab-grown meat is more environmentally friendly when compared to natural meat. The wastage of water is a significant issue all over the World and an even larger problem in the production of conventional meat. Furthermore, Lab-grown meat will greatly reduce the quantity of water usage, to produce 1 pound or approximately half a kilo of traditional meat requires more than 9,085 litres, in comparison to lab-grown meat only 95 litres of water is required. According to the study, we might save more water merely by not eating traditional meat. Lab-grown can greatly reduce this issue. Firstly, lab-grown meat is being created in a lab implying little water is required.

It removes the need for livestock, which can reduce the usage of energy as far as 45 per cent, decrease the use of land by 99 per cent, and produce up to 96 per cent fewer greenhouse gases, and 96 per cent lesser water usage depending upon the traditional meat product in comparison. It will

likewise be animal friendly as animals will not be abused or treated improperly.

Freshwater withdrawals per kilogram of food product

Freshwater withdrawals are measured in liters per kilogram of food product.

Source: Poore, J., & Nemecek, T. (2018). Reducing food's environmental impacts through producers and consumers. CC BY
 Note: Data represents the global average freshwater withdrawals from food products based on a large meta-analysis of food production covering 38,700 commercially viable farms in 119 countries.

Water pollution: The livestock industry utilizes a great deal of water for animal feed production, animal rearing, and hygiene. Water reused from animal manure is presently responsible for around 33percent of global nitrogen as well as phosphorous pollution, 50 percent of antibiotic pollution, and 37 percent of toxic heavy metals polluting global freshwater. Moreover, around 37 percent of pesticides which end up in the world’s freshwater resources have their source in the production of animal feed. In Spite Of high ambiguity, the conclusion is that the environmental effects of lab-grown meat production are significantly lower than traditionally produced meat.

LAB GROWN MEAT PRODUCING COMPANIES WORLDWIDE -2019

There are currently many companies that work on bringing lab-grown meat as well as seafood products to consumer markets globally. Here is a list of amazing companies producing these products:

SNO	COUNTRY	COMPANIES	PRODUCT	DESCRIPTION
1	INDIA	CLEAR MEAT	Cell cultured chicken.	Clear Meat is developing cell based chicken kheema biryani, a popular Indian dish that features minced chicken. By working on minced meat to start, Clear Meat founders have stated they will be able to spend less R&D time and capital to get to market faster. Clear Meat plans to have products available in 2022 in restaurants and retail channels.
2	USA	BALLETIC FOODS	Cell based meat (unsure of specific meats)	Balletic Foods is a cell-cultured meat technology startup currently operating in stealth mode with no investments or advancements announced to date.
3	USA	BLUE NALU	Cell based fish/seafood	BlueNalu is a cell based fish company and will eventually manufacture cell based seafood products. BlueNalu is developing a technology platform that will enable the company to cultivate a range of fresh-water and salt-water species of fish through a process the company calls "cellular aquaculture." This process includes the synthesis of muscle cells, connective tissue, and fat cells to cultivate fish products that taste identical to their wild caught counterpart.
4	USA	BOND PET FOOD	Acellular cultured pet food (meat proteins).	Bond Pet Foods is developing cell cultured proteins to be incorporated into pet food products. Instead of tissue engineering, the company uses DNA from a heritage hen as the blueprint for protein development.
5	USA	FINLESS FOODS	Cell based fish production (bluefin tuna)	Finless Foods is developing cell based fish and seafood with its immediate focus on cultivating bluefin tuna cells. Bluefin tuna is one of the most expensive and overfished varieties of fish on the market and contains high levels of mercury.
6	USA	JUST	Cell based beef (waygu).	JUST where the company makes plant based eggs, mayo, dressing and cookie dough. JUST stated they would be entering into the cell based meat space starting with the production of cell cultured chicken nuggets and eventually moving into the production of cell cultured Wagyu beef.
7	USA	MEMPHIS MEAT	Cell based meat (general meats).	Memphis Meats is arguably the most famous cell based meat company in part because of notable investors including Bill Gates and Richard Branson. Memphis Meats has successfully cultivated and harvested cell-based beef, chicken, and duck inside of bioreactors.

8	USA	MISSION BARNS	Cell based meat (general meats)	Mission Barns is a cell based tech company focused on producing flavor in the form of cell cultured fat. The company is working on developing bacon and duck fat working exclusively with fat cells as opposed to muscle cells that make up the bulk of animal tissue.
9	USA	NEW AGE MEATS	Cell based pork.	New Age Meats where the company uses automation & data science to develop cell-cultured meat. New Age is currently working on developing pork sausage. The company released their first sausage prototype in September 2018, only 10% cultured pig cells (the remaining 90% was plant based). The company used fetal bovine serum to make these cultured pig cells, which they are currently working to replace.
10	USA	WILD EARTH	Acellular cultured mouse cells for pet food.	Wild Earth uses cellular fermentation to cultivate Koji, a high protein fungus that the company blends into pet treats and food. Wild Earth treats are currently on the market being sold online, at select brick-and-mortar retail stores, and wholesale to pet food retailers. Koji, the star ingredient in Wild Earth's pet food formula is very efficient to grow and scale and requires significantly fewer resources than meat.
11	USA	WILD TYPE	Cell based meat (unsure of specific meats).	Wild Type is developing cell cultured salmon, Just over a pound of cell based salmon was produced for the tasting, which reportedly took three and a half weeks to grow. Wild Type plans to start with the introduction of smaller quantities of minced salmon where the meat is mixed with sauce. From there, they are targeting lox for bagels, and eventually, salmon filets. The company is aiming to produce full slabs of lab-grown salmon.
12	ISRAEL	ALEPH FARMS	Cell based meat (steak).	Aleph Farms is a cell based meat company, focused on steak production. That relies on the natural process of cellular regeneration occurring in cows to build three dimensional tissues.
13	ISRAEL	BIOFOOD SYSTEMS	Cell based meat (beef).	BioFood Systems is developing cell based meat using bovine embryonic stem cells. According to BioFood Systems website, the company has a patented process to cultivate bovine stem cells using an animal free cell culture media.
14	ISRAEL	FUTURE MEAT TECHNOLOGIES	Cell based chicken.	Future Meat Technologies has a proprietary technology for growing fibroblast cells inside of bioreactor systems. Fibroblasts are connective tissue cells (like those found underneath the skin) that grow rapidly and can be differentiated into fat or muscle cells without any genetic modification or foreign genetic material added. The fat and muscle cells are then grown in a bioreactor using animal free cell culture medium that Future Meat has developed and patented. The company has also developed a process for cleaning toxic waste (a major challenge involved in producing cell-based meat) and recycling the medium to improve efficiency and reduce costs. This proprietary cleaning process is like a water filtration system that contains solid particles that bind to the toxic waste molecules (mostly ammonia) and filters them out of the bioreactor.
15	ISRAEL	MEATECH	Cell based meat.	MeaTech is developing a 3D stem cell printing technology for cell based meat production.
16	ISRAEL	SUPER MEAT	Cell based chicken.	SuperMeat working to develop a meal-ready chicken cultured meat product created through the use of cell culture.

17	NETHERLANDS	MEATABLE	Cell based beef.	Meatable is licensing a proprietary technology called,OPTi-OX to develop cell based meat. OPTi-OX is a form of genetic intervention that converts pluripotent stem cells into any desired cell type. This means that Meatable can take a stem cell sourced from a calf's umbilical cord and reprogram the cell to turn into a fat cell or a muscle cell — two types of cells that are found in every meat product.
18	NETHERLANDS	MOSA MEATS	Cell based beef.	Mosa Meat was the pioneering company responsible for the very first lab-grown hamburger.
19	CANADA	APPLETON FARMS	Cell based beef.	Appleton Meats is focused on the production and scaling of ground beef. Appleton Meat Company uses a Clean Meat biotechnological platform to produce meat which is grown in breweries, thus eliminating the need for livestock.
20	CANADA	FUTURE FIELDS	Cell based chicken.	Future Fields is developing animal-free cell culture media suitable for growing chicken cells. Future Fields plans to sell this input to other cellular agriculture and biotech companies to progress the overall cell based meat industry. Future Fields also plans to use the animal-free media to cultivate their own cell based chicken, which the company plans to sell to secondary processors to start.
21	CANADA	SEAFUTURE	Cell based fish.	Seafuture is a biotech company that uses cell culturing technology to produce seafood that consistently and sustainably meet global demand while relieving the pressure on our ocean ecosystems.
22	JAPAN	INTEGRICULTURE	Cell based meat (unsure of specific meats).	IntegriCulture has developed a proprietary technology system to produce cell-based meat. Currently, IntegriCulture is focusing on the production of cultured foie gras.
23	JAPAN	NISSIN FOODS GROUP	Cell based meat.	Nissin foods to produce diced steak using cell-based technology. The research group had success in the maturation process of bovine muscle cells feeding the cells vitamin C and using collagen gel as a scaffold structure.
24	SINGAPORE	SHIOK MEATS	Cell based seafood.	Shiok Meats is developing cell-based shrimp prawns, crabs, and lobster. To start, Shiok is focusing on shrimp and unveiled its first prototype in April 2019, which lacked texture and was a meat slurry formed into a shrimp dumpling yet retained shrimp flavor and scent. Shiok is focusing on making a more structured shrimp product for a higher end market but would not have a shell or eyeballs and just be the edible tissue portion.

25	SPAIN	BIOTECH FOODS	Cell based pork	BioTech Foods is a b2b cultured meat company based in Spain. The company is working with pork muscle cells to make ground meat to be incorporated into a variety of products such as sausages and meatballs.
26	SPAIN	CUBIQ FOODS	Cell based animal fats	CUBIQ FOODS is the first European producer of cell-based fat. The company plans to develop and commercialize cell-based fat to enhance the flavor of food and add essential fatty acids (omega-3) to food products.
27	FRANCE	GOURMEY	Cell based foie gras	Gourmey is developing cell based foie gras. The company plans to source cells from duck eggs and feed the cells proteins, lipids, and vitamins that mimic the natural diet of the duck when eating oats, corn or grass to cultivate fatty liver cells.
28	AUSTRALIA	HEUROS	Cell cultured media.	Heuros is developing cell culture medium that does not contain fetal bovine serum, genetic engineering, recombinant growth factors, pluripotent stem cells, steroids, or antibiotics. Heuros plans to supply their cell culture medium to other cellular agriculture companies working on culturing muscle cells.
29	AUSTRALIA	VOW	Cell based kangaroo meat.	VOW is developing cell-based kangaroo meat. In 2019, the company unveiled the first prototype, which was a few grams of kangaroo meat made into steamed dumplings. VOW is the first company we have seen taking a unique approach to cellular agriculture by cultivating species of meat not commonly consumed.
30	CHINA	AVANT MEATS	Cell based meat (unsure of specific meats).	Avant Meats is developing cell cultured fish maw (aka dried fish bladder), a delicacy in traditional Chinese cuisine. Fish maw is typically sourced from either the Chinese Bahaba (giant yellow croaker) or the Totoaba, both of which are on the brink of extinction due to such high demand for fish maw. Avant Meats will source cells from the Chinese Bahaba fish.
31	UNITED KINGDOM	HIGHER STEAKS	Cell cultured beef.	HigherSteaks is developing cell-based meat with an initial focus on pork sausage and pork minced meat. HigherSteaks plans to then move towards production more structured meat like chicken breasts and steaks after the success of their minced meat products.
32	BELGIUM	PEACE OF MEAT	Foie gras and chicken.	Peace of Meat is a B2B cultured meat production company focusing on a multitude of cultured meat products
33	RUSSIA	OCHAKOV FOOD INGREDIENTS	Cell cultured beef.	Ochakov Food Ingredients Plant announced the successful cultivation of cell-based meatloaf.
34	ARGENTINA	CRAVERI LABORATORIES (BIFE)	Cell cultured beef.	BIFE is the first and only company based in Argentina working on cell-based meat. Argentina is a major global beef supplier and in 2019 became the leading exporter of beef to China by a small fraction skirting past Brazil.
35	TURKEY	BIFTEK	Cell cultured beef.	Biftek is a cell based meat company currently focused on developing a cell culture medium that does not include fetal bovine serum, to efficiently cultivate beef cells. Currently, Biftek.co is testing a variety of different cocktails or media blends to find the most efficient and least expensive blend for cultivating beef tissue cells.

INTRODUCTION OF LAB GROWN MEAT IN INDIA

Lab-Grown meat research and development has proved to be happening in the western world for many years now. And right now, it has intrigued the interest of Indian researchers who have now begun working on producing plant-based lab-grown meat. India started working in the direction of producing minced clean chicken meat products which are tailor-made for the Indian market. The first product is going to be chicken Kheema Biryani minced chicken rice along with exotic Indian spices. Lab grown meat is currently developing cell-based chicken kheema Biryani, a very popular Indian dish which features minced chicken. Through working on minced meat to begin. The taste is going to be the same due to the fact that lab grown meat is meat. Though, rather than slaughtering a whole animal for the various part of its body, the technology in lab grown meat could develop those portions based upon a biopsy taken from various parts of the animals' body. Lab-grown "**clean meat**" might become available in India by 2025, thus enabling consumers the opportunity to enjoy animal products without encouraging cruel as well as unjustifiable industrial animal agriculture.

POTENTIAL EFFECTS IN AGRICULTURAL SECTOR

From an Indian perspective, it is necessary to take into consideration the possible effect that lab-grown meats would have in the agricultural sector, especially on economics as well as employment. Agriculture, as well as food production, make up an important role in our country's GDP, as well as our overall employment. People who work within the sector are concentrated primarily in rural areas which are almost entirely dependent on agriculture. Any significant changes in food production, as well as consumption, would certainly have a profound effect on these individuals, regions, and communities.

HOW THE LAB GROWN MEAT (CULTURED MEAT) REVOLUTION IMPACTS INDIAN FARMING SECTOR

Lab-grown meat substitutes have exploded because of two different trends increasing demand for meat and increasing fears about meat. Animal farming is a developing economic center globally powered by growing demand in both developed and developing countries. Although it is additionally a cause of great concern regarding public health, worker safety, climate change as

well as animal cruelty. The researchers expect cultured meat will substitute 50% of the global meat intake by the middle of the present century.

Currently, in India, individuals who are employed in the agriculture sector or those who operate small local farms, are the primary meat and food suppliers. Their earnings vary depending on people who consume natural food which has been cultivated on farm fields. Although, it all could be brought to an end because farmers may be facing the possibility for a future radical shift about how their customers interact with them if lab-grown meat is set to become popular. At the end of the 21st century, researchers predict intensive animal farming is going to be gradually phased out completely and all meat will be cultivated in factories. Millions of people, employed in agriculture and food processing, will ultimately lose their jobs. Due to the fact that the new processes are so effective and efficient, the employment they generate will not be able to match the employment they destroy. Worse yet, the necessity to have farms could become irrelevant in the near future because of this breakthrough.

NATURAL MEAT MIGHT BECOME A LUXURY MEAT – INCREASED PRICES WILL BE A POSITIVE TO THE FARMERS

If the trend of lab-grown meat will continue to be developed and then if it achieves the goal of mass adoption, the cost of naturally grown meat is going to rise immensely. Meaning, that the meat which is directly originated from animals is going to become a luxury that will just be affordable to a tiny percentage of the population. Whether this is going to be the reality the future will bring, farmers are going to have mixed feelings about the entire situation. First, they are going to lose a big share of their market which consists of average middle and poor class consumers because they will be compelled to consume lab-grown meat because of the increase in the price of natural animal meat. On one hand, such as in any industry which is high-end, they may develop a tiny but solid pool of customers who are going to become consistent buyers of natural foods merely because they prefer natural meat and they are able to pay for it.

LIVESTOCK MAINTENANCE WILL BE LESS EXPENSES

Since animals will no longer have to be butchered because of the unique method of growing lab meat, farmers are going to have the luxury to decrease the total management costs of their farms.

This is because, to begin the process of growing lab-grown meat, only a small part of cells will have to be removed from an animal that is a painless procedure for farm animals. Due to the fact that farmers are going to be able to prevent the slaughter of animals, they would be able to decrease their livestock sizes and then double down on retaining their select few herds.

NEW REVOLUTION WILL CHANGE THE APPROACH TO FARMING AND INDIAN AGRICULTURE SECTOR

The processes which are currently being used in the farming sector are obliged to significantly change if the concept of lab-grown meat turns into a reality. Rather than raising cattle the usual ways or by using the non-sustainable synthetic methods of raising livestock, farmers will have the ability to concentrate more on naturalness and quality, instead of grouping animals in cruel conditions to make the most value. This trend will similarly impact the Large farms as well as their immoral processes of farming which are present in a certain quantity of commercial farms that will be compelled to change.

THE FATE OF ANIMALS AND FARMERS DUE TO LAB GROWN MEAT REVOLUTION

Due to the new revolution of lab-grown meat livestock are predicted to be either abandoned to die or else released into the wild. The appropriate time frame for lab-grown meat makes this consideration likely. By optimistic predictions, large-scale production is likely to happen only a few years away. When new processes have been adopted, the requirement for farm animals will slowly decline. Less animals are going to be grown, and therefore the animals in the middle of these issues will never exist. Many individuals are also worried about the adverse impact a shift to lab-grown meat might have on farmers. However, the new technology is not the only danger farmers now face as the entire industry is becoming increasingly centralized. Moreover, lab-grown meat offers a new industry, along with opportunities to grow and process products that can be used in cellular agriculture. The meat processing industry could learn a lesson from the way in which taxis lost out to Ola as well as Uber they need to adapt to the new technologies to survive and prosper. The farming industry has already been taking measures in the same direction.

LAB GROWN MEAT CONSUMPTION AND RELIGION

Lab-grown meat, as with any other new technology, presents several philosophical, ethical, and religious queries. Primarily because of its vague status, religious authorities are still discussing the following: Is it in lab-grown meat is Kosher consumable under Jewish dietary laws, Halal for Muslim consumers, in compliance with Islamic laws, or else what should be done if there's no animal available for ritual practices for Hindu consumers. Regarding the Jewish religion, rabbinical opinion is split up. Some believe that cultured meat may only be regarded as Kosher when the original cells had been extracted from a slaughtered Kosher animal. Other People suppose that regardless of the origin of cells that are used to produce the lab-grown meat, they will definitely lose their initial identity. Consequently, the end result cannot be specified as prohibited for consumption.

With regard to the Islamic community, the essential issue is whether the lab-grown meat is in compliance with Islamic laws or not, most frequently referred to as Halal or not. Because lab-grown meat culturing is the latest innovation, the traditional Islamic legal scholar that Muslims frequently refer to never before has discussed its Halal status. Hence, current Islamic jurists have carried on this task. The Halal status of lab-grown meat can be resolved by pinpointing the source of the cells as well as serum medium that is used by culturing the artificial lab-grown meat. Consequently, in vitro meat is regarded as Halal only in cases where the stem cell is extracted from a Halal slaughtered animal, as well as neither blood nor serum has been used in the process. In Fact, the serum must be avoided unless a person can demonstrate that the meat will not be altered as a consequence of contact with the serum being potentially unclean.

DUE TO LAB-GROWN MEAT LIST OF OCCUPATIONS MOST LIKELY IMPACTED

Lab-grown meat has an impact on almost all farming and related sectors. An economist estimates that 50 percent of positions are at risk, because of new lab-grown meat food technology. However, a few businesses may be more related to the local market and people find it very difficult to change the traditional method of food to adapt to modern food. In the very near future, we expect to see a decrease in the number of unskilled labourers in farming and agricultural positions, so many of those positions have been gradually eliminated due to increased modern food process system.

Researchers and Robots are able to handle tasks within the modern food process factory more safely and efficiently. On top of this, the Meat industries are most vulnerable within the farming sector, and farm feeds agricultural sectors.

THE IMPACTS OF LAB-GROWN MEAT ON THE ECONOMY OF INDIA

The transformation of the whole systems of production, governance, as well as management of the lab-grown meat, provides a broad range of the challenges and opportunities in the job, along with both direct and indirect effects on sectors throughout the economy of agriculture, farming, and related services and types of workers among them, the most vulnerable categories include youth, women, etc. Technological innovations may be supported by the structural change of the country's economy. Moving away from traditional farming to manufacturing farming helps to promote the rural labour movement of workers to modern food manufacturing sectors.

GLOBAL CONSUMER MARKET OF LAB-GROWN MEAT

The global lab-grown meat market is projected to be valued at USD 214 million in 2025 and is expected to reach USD 593 million around 2032, recording a CAGR of 15.7 percent from 2025 to 2032 in the ordinary situation. Reasons such as the increasing intake of meat combined with the growing demand for nutritional meat is expected to drive the rise of the lab-grown meat industry throughout the prediction period.

POULTRY SECTOR: the poultry sector is taken into consideration for the largest stake in 2021. The poultry sector accounted for a large stake in the global lab-grown meat market, based upon the source, in 2021 because of the high fondness of chicken products in the nugget shape in popular food chains like KFC. The lab-grown chicken products are anticipated to have a cheaper price when compared to alternative sources and achieve widespread popularity around the world. Furthermore, the growing demand for chicken meat, due to the fast-growing urban population in developing nations, is anticipated to contribute to the lab-grown meat market worldwide.

NUGGET SEGMENT: the nugget segment in the lab-grown meat market is forecasted to increase at the maximum CAGR in the prediction period. Based upon the end-user, the lab-grown meat market is divided into nuggets, meatballs, burgers, hot dogs, and sausage. Nearly All of the restaurants, as well as hotels, provide chicken products in the form of nuggets, because of the rising

convenience of eating meat as well as its low cost, in comparison to other chicken products. This gives rise to the increasing use of lab-grown meat in the nuggets segment. The increasing developments of eating on-the-go food products additionally make nuggets, a preferred option for consumers. Major fast-food retailers like KFC and supermarkets are similarly providing chicken nuggets, as customers choose to spend on ready to eat food products rather than cooking.

PROACTIVE POLICY MAKING BY GOVERNMENT

- Decreasing the number of animals farmed for the meat would constitute considerable progress made in fulfilling the India objective of reducing greenhouse gas emissions by 2030. Policymakers can seek to participate in these benefits for the environment by facilitating the development of lab-grown cultured meat as well as its launch on the market, while also facilitating the transition for farmers, that are currently dependent upon livestock farming, in the direction of new types of economic activity.
- Through supporting their very own research into lab-grown meat, Our central and State government will be seizing the opportunity to commit themselves in a particular area of technological development with enormous potential for a positive effect, and to contribute towards a developing new market in the food industry. There is also the option for creating new jobs in this field despite the fact that these would need different skills, as well as the retraining of modern technologies.
- Additionally, we might be able to recognize areas that are dependent on livestock farming and take into account the manner in which their homegrown economies might be diversified. Where the circumstances allow, farmers could be supported during the transition from livestock farming to growing crops. These may be crops used for human consumption, which is more space and water effective than livestock rearing, or else for biofuels, that would work to achieve the country ultimate objective of increasing the contribution of renewable energy sources, for example, the biofuels, for the transportation of fuel mix.
- Policymakers may also take proactive measures to ensure that if lab-grown cultured meat is available-for-sale, customers are properly informed about the product that they are buying. This could include controlling whether lab-grown meat is going to be sold as a

distinct product to conventional meat, as well as how this difference between the two is suggested to consumers.

- At the Same Time, the development of lab-grown meat is commonly seen in a positive way by environmental activists, the immediate future of lab-grown meat will eventually rely on the extent to which the broader public is ready to go along with this brand-new lab-grown meat food and adapt their eating habits.

CONCLUSION:

Lab-grown meat production is an innovative technology with several advantages. This is a significant technology for dealing with a broad range of environmental as well as food security concerns. By preserving agricultural resources as well as reducing key sources of water and air pollution, lab-grown meat will decrease the environmental effects of food production and will contribute to a wide variety of sustainability objectives. Productivity improvements in land and water usage will also contribute to conservation. Lab-grown meat offers many opportunities to decrease the carbon emissions of the food system, safeguarding against climate change. And removing manure as well as antibiotic growth agents will help to improve the health of rural communities, restore waterways, and guarantee the effectiveness of life-saving drugs. There is also the option for creating new jobs in this field despite the fact that these would need different skills, as well as the retraining of modern technologies. Present lab-grown meat production technologies are appropriate for larger-scale commercial production at an affordable cost. Some more efforts are needed for lowering the expense of production to be able to make it affordable compared to present traditional meat. The lab-grown meat is definitely a benefit to humanity and will play an important role in food, dietary as well as ecological sustainability and security. Consumer acceptance, safety, and security of lab-grown meat as well as consumer education will have to be concentrated on utilizing the advantages of lab-grown meat. Lab-grown meat is going to be a powerful environmentally sustainable tool for businesses, cities, as well as nations to build a healthier, more effective, and efficient, as well as a more civilized food system.

REFERENCES:

- [1] SYNTHEGO- The bench by Amanda Mahi, <https://www.synthego.com/blog/>
- [2] <https://www.rethinkx.com/press-release/2019/9/16/new-report-major-disruption-in-food-and-agriculture-in-next-decade>
- [3] How the Trend of Cultured Meat Will Affect Farmers by Carlos Miskinis - <https://www.challenge.org/>
- [4] Cultured Meat in Islamic Perspective. Hamdan MN, Post MJ, Ramli MA, Mustafa AR J Relig Health. 2018 Dec; 57(6):2193-2206.
- [5] Krautwirth R. Will Lab-Grown Meat Find Its Way to Your Table? YU Observer (2018). Available online at: <https://yuobserver.org/2018/05/will-lab-grown-meat-find-way-table/> (accessed July 17, 2019).
- [6] Meat 2.0 : Are Lab Grown Meat Halal? January 23, 2019 | Hayatun Razak <https://emag.live/>
- [7] A culture of cultured meat: Better than animal agriculture By Matti Wilks March 8, 2019 – Green Biz <https://www.greenbiz.com/article/culture-cultured-meat-better-animal-agriculture>
- [8] From lab to table: Will cell-cultured meat win over Americans-By Laura Reiley May 4, 2019 <https://www.washingtonpost.com/business/2019/05/03/lab-table-will-cell-based-meat-win-over-americans/>
- [9] <https://www.mosameat.com/benefits/>
- [10] WORLD ANIMAL PROTECTION- 7 reasons why lab-grown meat will be better 04/10/2018
- [11] <https://ourworldindata.org/environmental-impacts-of-food>
- [12] RESEARCH AND MARKETS – The world’s largest market research store- Cultured Meat Market by Source (Poultry, Beef, Seafood, Pork, and Duck), End-Use (Nuggets, Burgers, Meatballs, Sausages, Hot Dogs), and Region (North America, Europe, Asia Pacific, Middle East & Africa, South America) - Global Forecast to 2032-ID: 4844553 Report September 2019 Region: Global, North America, Europe, Asia Pacific, Middle East, Africa 182 Pages Markets and Markets. <https://www.researchandmarkets.com/reports/>
- [13] Here Are 5 Things You Should Know About Lab-grown Meat- By Donovan Alexander December 12, 2018- Interesting Engineering
- [14] <https://www.four-paws.org/campaigns-topics/topics/nutrition/clean-meat-details>

About Author: **A. SHAJI GEORGE** M.A, M.B.A, MCA, MSc IT, MPhil, PhD.

Shaji George is a recognized technical expert in IT Infrastructure Systems, Network & Telecommunication, having worked in almost every aspect of the IT Industry. His research interests include Wireless, Networking, Cloud Computing, Big Data, Data Mining, Automation systems, Microeconomics, Gig Economy, Industrial Revolution 4.0, and Labour Economics.